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The Role of French in Mysore's Struggle with East India Company: A Reappraisal

Dr. Brijesh Kumar Shukla*

Abstract:

The relation between the state of Mysore under Haider Ali & his son Tipu sultan and the French have attracted more scholarly attention compared to any other Franco-Indian power relations. But the context of the studies mostly has been either limited to emphasize the modernization efforts of Mysore rulers or the possible attempt to refute English efforts to bring the challenging Indian power under its reign. The present paper aims at uncovering the outcome of the diplomatic dimensions of Franco-Mysore relationship and the follies on part of French to make use of most favourable moments. And also, how the English use this entire French bugaboo to justify their over aggressiveness and expansionism. The present paper will also try to evaluate some recent thoughts on Franco-Mysore relations that the French vision on Mysore was rather defensive, seeing its potential as a diversion to keep the England occupied in the Indian Ocean and to prevent them from occupying dominating role in European politics. They did not provide Mysore any direct military help rather through their promises of help kept Tipu pumped up against the English. Another factor which proved disastrous for the cause of Mysore was the involvement of some individuals of suspicious integrity in diplomatic negotiation with the native powers. Especially Ripaud and Malartic played very ignominious role. Their irresponsible acts became the immediate cause of its destruction of Mysore.

Keywords: Franco-Mysore relations, Lord Wellesley, Malartic's Proclamation

* Assistant Professor, Department of History, Shri Baldev P.G. College, Varanasi, U.P.

Introduction:

For their life time goals of fighting the English, both the state of Mysore and the French had nurtured high hopes on each other. The French saw in Mysore a formidable and dependable ally which can be depended upon to stop the English juggernaut in India and thus check the increasing influence of England in European politics. At the same time rulers of Mysore looked upon French as an ally who can, not only save Mysore from the clutches of East India Company but also turn Mysorean army into a formidable force with their modern weaponry and war tactics. For nearly 50 years both the parties kept on assuring each other of their support, but as we know nothing materialized on ground. This notion of friendship could not bore any fruit for any of them and at last both perished.

I

It won't be out of place to briefly explain the French relations with Mysore during the time of Haider Ali. There were two common bonds between Haider and the French. Naturally, the first was their perpetual hatred for the English nation. The other was political and military requirement. French were the main suppliers of European ammunition and trainers of native army and in return Haider gave them preferential treatment and opportunity in the merchandise of Malabar Coast. Therefore, the French and Haider were natural ally.

When the hostilities between the EIC and Haider erupted into First Anglo Mysore war in 1757, Haider Ali immediately requested Law de Lauriston, the French governor of Pondicherry for military support. A historian claims that Haider made this appeal with the conviction that French owe this help to him since he has earlier helped the French against English.² In his letter Haider proposed to pay any expenses incurred by troops sent from

²*The History of Hyder Shah alias Hyder Ali Khan Bahadur and his son Tipu Sultan*, by M.M.D.L.T., General in the Army of the Mogul Empire, revised and corrected by Prince Gholam Mohamed, 1855, reprint, Delhi: Cosmo, 1976, p. 139

Versailles to India to help him. He also submitted that this dispatch of military aid may be carried in secrecy, in case the prevailing peace in Europe somehow hampers this negotiation.

Law could not do much to help Haider but admire his efforts to contest the English. His dilapidated military and financial condition crippled his plans to assist.³ Moreover there were clear instructions from home government to not get involved in any local dispute till the time France and England were at peace.

Notwithstanding the absence of help from the French, Haider attacked the company's possession in south India and achieved considerable success. Impact of these victories was felt in London too as EIC's shares crashed.⁴ Anglo Mysore war ended with an edge to Haider and culminated with a treaty that had terms regarding exchange of prisoners and restoration of territories won.⁵ This war had provided the French the opportunity to launch their 'Revanche' and deliver a blow to East India Company but they missed.⁶ Though the chance was missed but Versailles administration moved a step forward towards forming an alliance with Haider Ali with the

³AN Col. C² 123, f. 33-48 Vo, V.G. Hatakhar (tr. & ed.) (1984). *French Records: Relating to the History of Marathas* (IX Volumes). (Hereafter FRENCH RECORDS).
Maharashtra State Board for Literature-culture

⁴ 'Bursting of the 'Bengal bubble'' is the term used by Nick Robins as the share price of East India Company fell 16 per cent in a single month. Robins, Nick. (2012). *The Corporation That Changed the World: How the East India Company Shaped the Modern Multinational*, Second Edition, PlutoPress. p. 85

⁵ Mazumdar, R.C., Raychaudhuri, H.C. & Dutta, K. (1953). *An Advanced History of India*, McMillon & Co. p. 683

⁶ 'Revanche' from England had been the focal point of French foreign policy in post Seven Year's war. Abarca, R. (1970). Classical Diplomacy and Bourbon "Revanche" Strategy, 1763-1770. *The Review of Politics*, 32(3), 313-337. Retrieved May 24, 2020, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1405914>.

dispatch of Hugel to India.⁷ these efforts were definitely in line with the French government's efforts to cultivate the friendship of Mysore.⁸ Here after, in France there was a general opinion of friendship towards India and Indians. In subsequent years many diplomatic initiatives were taken by the French officials in India to cultivate the friendship of Haider Ali but they failed. As every time Mysorean ruler asked for military support which was not fulfilled by the French home government.

II

By 1778 the situation in south India changed. English in India were in most distressed condition. Marathas and Haider Ali both had inflicted some crushing defeats to the East India Company. Three major powers of Deccan had come together in 1779 to form a *Grand Alliance* against the English company and posed serious threat to English presence in South India. With the French aid, English were to be attacked from three sides. But English diplomacy did manage to sabotage this alliance before it could actually damage the EIC in south.⁹

Meanwhile in 1779, in Isle of France change of command took place and another pro-revanche Souillac succeeded Dumas. With British under pressure in South India and Souillac having defences at Isles improved, seized this opportunity to enter into negotiations with Haider through Piveron De Morlat the French agent at Haider's court.¹⁰

During negotiations itself, a strong fleet under the command of D'Orves appeared off the Madras coast on 28 February 1781. He was instructed by Souillac not to land his troops and to be back by April. The purpose of

⁷AN Col. C 118, f. 44-48 Vo, Law's letter dated February 9, 1771, to M. le Duc de Praslin, Minister for the Navy, French Records, Vol. III & IV, pp.8-9

⁸ A.N. Colonies, C 118, f. 48-48V Letter From M. de Boynes, Minister for the Navy to Law dated 24th January 1772

⁹ Sen, S.P. *The French in India*. op. cit. pp. 18-19

¹⁰ French Records, Vol. VII, p. 9

sending this strong fleet was symbolic and they were not supposed to engage. They were here to make only a 'political demonstration... to show the Indian princess forces would give them confidence in our power.'¹¹

When D'Orves arrived, there was no English fleet on Coromandel Coast. English commander was caught between the Haider and French forces at Cuddalore. This was perfect timing for strike. Haider requested for action but D'Orves didn't respond. Then Haider further requested French fleet to at least remain there for some time so that English troops can be starved and defeated by cutting of their supplies thus dealing a decisive blow to English expansionism in India. But D'Orves character did not match the opportunity, rather than showing courage and boldness; he pleaded his instructions and sailed away. This was a blunder committed by French admiral. English army was gifted time and opportunity to put things in order. Later, for his timidity D'Orves was criticised by Souillac but the moment of Glory had passed.¹² The desertion of D'Orves infuriated Haider Ali and he refused to conclude the formal treaty of alliance.¹³

Home government, worried by this development, decided to send a powerful expedition force to India. The tension in Franco-Mysore relations eased with the arrival of French fleet under Admiral de Suffren, one of the greatest seamen France ever produced.¹⁴ But due to erroneous tactical decisions French fleet could not fulfill its purpose of display of their military capabilities.

French further disappointed Haider by sending only 3,000 troops under a mediocre commander Duchemin whereas former has demanded for 10000 men.¹⁵ Even then, Haider provided them one month's provisions and one

¹¹ Malleon, G.B. *Final French Struggles...* op. cit., p.9

¹² Sinha, N.K. (1941). *Haider Ali*, A Mukherjee & Co. p. 226

¹³ Sen, S.P. *The French in India*. op. cit. p. 276

¹⁴ Richmond, Herbert. (1931). *The Navy in India 1763-1783*. Ernest Benn. p. 234

¹⁵ Malleon, G.B. *Final French Struggles..*, p.29

lakh rupees on arrival.¹⁶ But, Duchemin kept demanding more money for expenses and also did not adhere to Haider's strategic plans.¹⁷ But the news of Bussy's arrival with large expeditionary force at Isle of France in June 1782 enroute to India eased the tensed Franco Mysore relations. Before anything materialized on ground Haider Ali died on December 7th 1782 and was succeeded by Tipu Sultan.

III

After his much-delayed arrival in India with a meagre force with him, Bussy developed differences with Tipu over silly issues such as not given a grand reception. He had the naval support of Admiral De Suffren who urged for the action. But the veteran general did not move and decided to remain defensive. When English General Stuart stroked at Cuddalore and forced a battle on 7th June 1783, the French easily repulsed the invader proving their military might. Still, Bussy did not move out of his defences to chase down fleeing enemy troops.¹⁸ English at this moment were in most fragile state in South India.¹⁹ With the Mysore's troops present to assist French one decisive action by Bussy could have annihilated the English from South India. French let this golden opportunity slip out of their hands. With their unmilitary like decisions, French not only damaged there would be

¹⁶ Martineau, A. (ed.) (1932) *Journal de Bussy, commandant général des forces de terre et de mer dans l'Inde, 13 novembre 1781-31 mars 1783*. (Hereafter *Journal de Buss.*, Société de l'histoire de l'Inde française. Bibliothèque publique pp. 111- 113 as quoted in Sen, S.P. *The French in India*, op. cit., p. 279

¹⁷ Sen, S.P. *The French in India*. op. cit. p. 276

¹⁸ Mautort, Chevalier de. (1835). *Mémoires Du Chevalier De Mautort, Capitaine Au Régiment D'austrasie Hevalier De Lordre Royal Et Militaire De Saint-Louis (1752 — 1802)* (Memories of Chevalier de Mautort, Captain of the Austrasia Regiment — Knight of Lord Royal And Military of Saint-Louis (1752 - 1802)). p. 298; the writer was himself part of the French contingent.

¹⁹ Ibid.

prospects in India but also proved fatal to Tipu's interest. Tipu kept on waging war single handedly and kept the company into pressure.

Just at this time news arrived in Madras of the peace treaty of Versailles by which France and England agreed to cease all the hostilities across the globe.²⁰ This peace gave company the much-needed break to save itself from getting tarnished. Naturally English company welcomed it. But surprisingly French too were delighted at the peace. They simply missed the point that this war presented them the last chance to shift the balance of power in France's favour in India and may be in Europe too. In fact, while going through the events of Second Anglo-Mysore war it appears that French interest were negated more by the incompetency of Frenchman than their enemies.

At a time when fall of Mangalore was eminent, Bussy instructed small French force under Cossigny attached to Mysore army to stay away from any operation. Even French commanders like Lally²¹ and Bonde lot to whom Tipu was the paymaster refused to fight following their compatriot commander's orders. Cossigny too withdrew from the front. This unilateral withdrawal was surely an act of backstabbing.²²

After this whole episode, though the Mysorean ruler's faith was shattered, but he did not sever relations with them. He still wanted to unite himself closely with the French, by whose assistance he hoped to subvert the power he both feared and hated.²³ But the French, keeping relations with Mysore

²⁰ Roy, Kaushik. *War, Culture and Society in Early Modern South Asia*. op. cit. p. 86

²¹ It was only due to the instructions by the Bussy that Lally acted against the will of his employer. After this episode also, Lally served his master with loyalty and was effective in winning Travancore for Tipu in 1790. Even he lost his life fighting for Tipu in 1790. Lafont, Jean Marie (2000). *INDIKA: Essays in Indo-French Relation 1630-1976*, Manohar for Centre De Sciences Humaines. p. 156

²² Sen, S.P. *The French in India*, op. cit., p. 279

²³ Bowring, *Rulers of India: Haider Ali and Tipu Sultan*, op. cit., p. 137

on a lower frequency, tried to toe with Marathas. This paradigm shift in French policy clearly reveals that French remained inconsistent and immature towards their alliance with Mysore.

IV

The see-saw Franco-Mysore relationship went through a change in the coming years. Though Tipu was deeply disappointed with the French approach towards him, he still had hopes of French military support. He believed that the policy of French governors of Pondicherry or of Isles were unpredictable because they were mere servants of the French crown and were controlled by Versailles. To conclude a definite commercial and military alliance he decided to open direct negotiations with the French monarch Louis XVI.²⁴ He wanted to ascertain what help he could get, in case he attacked English.²⁵

In 1787 he decided to send an embassy to Louis XVI.²⁶ In a personal letter prince underlined the sacrifices made by Mysore against the fight to common enemy. He stressed upon the need of 'mutual friendship and renown'.²⁷ King showed great hospitality towards ambassadors but smartly avoided the proposal of alliance.²⁸ King knew France was on the eve of great social and political turmoil which limited the ambitions of king.

²⁴ Hasan, Mohibbul (1951). *History of Tipu Sultan*. The Bibliophile Ltd. p. 113

²⁵ Letter No. 108, Kirkpatrick, William (ed.) (1811). *Select Letters of Tipu Sultan to Various Functionaries*, London

²⁶ James, Gregory (1991). Tipu Sultan's embassy to the Court of Louis XVI: A double deception, *The Indian Historical Review*. XVII (1-2) (July 1990 & January 1991). 193-204. ICHR

²⁷ Kirkpatrick, *Select Letters of Tipu Sultan*, op. cit., No. 336

²⁸ For French response to Tipu during this period and subsequently see, Ray, Aniruddha (1993). French Attitude to Tipu Sultan: A General Review. In B. Sheikh Ali (ed.), *Tipu Sultan: a great Martyr*. pp. 51-76

Despite having good wishes for Tipu, Louis XVI never had the resources to help him. The ambassadors stayed for 03 months and returned to India in May 1789 with a few French craftsmen and lots of hollow promises.

Next year, when third Anglo-Mysore war broke out, Tipu again sought military help from Pondicherry but the French remained indifferent. He promised to protect Pondicherry in case of attack by the English. The France was in midst of Revolution thus no help came. Tipu alone had to wage the war but he could not sustain the combine onslaught of three adversaries and finally in 1792 had to purchase peace at a great cost. It can be concluded here that at the hour of need French could not and did not stand with Mysore, partly because of lack of resources. The indifference shown by them towards Tipu was a great blunder and was to definitely cost them dearly. Diplomatically and militarily, both ways, it was an act of folly that French allowed the annihilation of Tipu's power who was their most trustworthy friend in plan of contending the English power in India.

V

In the post-revolution period when monarchy was abolished in France in September 1792, all other major powers of Europe rallied against France. In France, entire social and political scene changed after the French revolution. The same turmoil took place in Mauritius (Isle of France) and Isle of Bourbon also. The revolutionary extremists established assembly of citizens which seized the power, thus breaking the entire governance structure and resulting into utter chaos and confusion.²⁹ Revolutionary France, baffling to handle its own problems, had little time and resources to devote to these tiny colonies. The citizens of these colonies had to take to adventurous privateering, at times even to piracy for their survival. One

²⁹ Sen, S.P. *The French in India*, op. cit., p. 548

such privateer Ripaud was to play an ingenious yet important role in future Franco-Mysore relations.³⁰

After few years of the treaty of Srirangapatam, Tipu had strengthened his position and was willing to turn the table on English. But there was no communication between France and Tipu post fall of Pondicherry.³¹ All links were cut. Tipu had no idea of the condition of Europe and the anarchical condition in the Isles of France and Bourbon.³²

When Ripaud accidentally reached Mysore and came to know about Tipu's eagerness to secure military help from French, sensed an opportunity and introduces himself as second-in-command of Isles.³³ He was taken to Tipu's *darbar* and was received with great honour. To win the trust of French at Tipu's court and faith of prince, he indoctrinated the French contingent on the lines of Revolutionary ideas and established a Jacobin club at Srirangapatam.³⁴ He also established the Revolutionary Tribunal on the lines of convention government's tribunals in France.³⁵ Many public ceremonies were organised by this Jacobin club.³⁶ In order to garnish revolutionary France's support Tipu participated in these activities with zeal.

³⁰Wilks, Mark. *Historical Sketches of the South of India, in an Attempt to Trace..*, Vol. II, op. cit., p. 307

³¹ Sen, S.P. *The French in India*, op. cit., pp. 549

³² Ibid.

³³Wilks, Mark. *Historical Sketches of the South of India, in an Attempt to Trace ...*, Vol II, p. 307

³⁴ Hasan, Mohibbul, *History of Tipu Sultan*, op. cit., p.150

³⁵ Proceedings of a Jacobin Club formed at Srirangapatam in '*Official Documents, relative to the negotiations carried on by Tippoo Sultaun...to which is added, Proceedings of a Jacobin Club, formed at Seringapatam by the French Soldiers in the Corps commanded by M. Dompert*, Calcutta, 1799 pp. 175-195

³⁶ Ibid

Tipu believed the words of Ripaud and decided to send an Embassy to Isles to find out more about the conditions at which this force will be available to him.³⁷ His ministers advised him against this is adventure as sending an Embassy to French would draw the immediate hostility of the English.³⁸ But the Sultan decided to move ahead.³⁹ Embassy left for Mauritius on 5th December 1798 and reached there on 19 January 1798. After the arrival Ripaud, who was supposed to mediate the alliance flew away and was never seen again.

Tipu's ambassadors were received with honours by governor Malartic.⁴⁰ But soon, they were disillusioned on finding that there was no army stationed as promised by Ripaud to Tipu, nor was there any hope.⁴¹ Malartic also accepted the fact that Ripaud has misled the prince and no such force is available at the island. But he promised to help.

Tipu had requested for the strictest secrecy of the mission but bereft of commonest political science, Malartic issued a proclamation to public asking the locals to enlist in Tipu service "who desires to expel the English from India".⁴² In response to this appeal only 99 volunteers enlisted that too many of them where the ordinary workers. This open proclamation served

³⁷ Marsh, Kate (2009). *Indian in the French Imagination: Peripheral Voices*, Pickering & Chatto. p. 17

³⁸ Wilks, Mark. *Historical Sketches of the South of India, in an Attempt to Trace ...*, Vol II, op. cit., p. 309

³⁹ Sheikh Ali, B. (1982). *Tipu Sultan: A Study in Diplomacy and Confrontation*, Geetha Book House. p. 288

⁴⁰ Gurwood, Col John (ed.) (M.DCCC.XLIV(1844)). *Arthur Wellesley-Duke of Wellington: The dispatches of Field Marshal the Duke of Wellington: Volume 1 of 8*. Parker, Furniwall and parker. p. 3

⁴¹ Wilks, Mark. *Historical Sketches of the South of India*. Vol II, p. 310

⁴² Concluding remarks in Malartic's proclamation, *Official Documents Relative to the Negotiations Carried on by Tippoo Sultaun with the French Nation and other Foreign States...* op. cit., pp. 27-28

no good to the Tipu but only made public Tipu's secret overtures to French.⁴³ In June 1798 itself the copies of proclamation had reached to Calcutta and London. It proved a catastrophe to Tipu. Wellesley made this an excuse to destroy Tipu. Tipu again tried to establish contacts with the *Executive Directory* of France and sent letters to them, but of no avail.

The foolishness of Malartic served the English more than Tipu. This whole episode became the propaganda point of English against Tipu. It resulted in declaration of war on Mysore in 1799, which ended with the death of Tipu Sultan in action. In this final battle Mysorean French party remained loyal to the Sultan.⁴⁴ They were decimated by the enemy's fire and bayoneted in close hand to hand fighting. Forrest records that only two trusted advisers remained to Tipu in these last days and one of them was French brigadier Chapuis.⁴⁵ Thus it can be concluded that in relation to Mysore French failed as nation but as individuals they earned a name for them. English Governor General Lord Wellesley, a diehard imperialist and expansionist, magnified this French presence in and used it as *casus belli* for his aggressive designs.

Conclusion

With survey of French relations with the state of Mysore it can be concluded that both the parties definitely had positive intentions to help each other. Definitely their intentions were derived from their vested common interests of halting English expansionism in India. Both of these powers admired and had firm belief in one another's ability. Probably this is what most of the historians on this subject have termed as Franco-Mysorean friendship. But the question that remains unanswered is, did it yield the desired outcomes?

⁴³ Heras, Father H (ed.) *Fort William India House Correspondence Vol - XVIII: 1796-1800 (Foreign, Political & Secret)*, pp-9-10

⁴⁴ Lafont, Jean Marie, *INDIKA*. op. cit., p. 156

⁴⁵ Forrest, G. *Tiger of Mysore* op. cit., p. 294

In my opinion, this friendship was a mere illusion only as its final outcome was null and void. Barring the instance of arrival of Suffren and Bussy, every plan remained in air only. It can be argued that French did regard and respect their promises and commitments but they always lacked the resources to standby their obligations.

It's a fact that with the political realities of Eighteenth-century India, Mysore was to perish a day but it was the French connection of Mysore that became the immediate cause of Fourth Anglo-Mysore war that resulted in the extinction of Mysore as independent state. Finally, I argue that with regard to Tipu's survival that the alliance with the French eventually turned out to be a great disadvantage because they not only kept away from any serious military assistance, but even provided an adequate pretext for the British to attack and destroy Tipu.

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